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Research Article

**EVALUATING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF LIVER
PRETREATMENT BIOPSY AND BASIC DIAGNOSIS OF
MENTAL HEALTH DISORDERS ON HEPATITIS C
TREATMENT****¹Dr Muhammad Farooq, ¹Dr Muhammad Junaid Khan, ¹Dr Waqas Khan,
²Dr Muhammad Ilyas, ³Dr Zia ur Rahman**¹Medical A Unit, MTI/MMC Mardan²Cardiology Unit, PIMS Islamabad³Nephrology Unit, MTI/LRH Peshawar**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: This survey was conducted to characterize overall treatment response and completion rates among the hepatitis C patient population in a metropolitan VA medical center. In addition, we investigated whether pre-treatment liver biopsy is a positive indicator of treatment completion and whether the presence of psychological well-being problems is a negative indicator of treatment completion.

Methods: The examination chart survey was conducted on the 375 patients who were treated for HCV and met the survey consideration limits between March 2019 to February 2020 at our foundation. Our current research was conducted at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from March 2019 to February 2020. Clinical information was obtained from the mechanized framework of patient records and was broken down for specific limitations.

Results. A continuous virologic reaction was observed in 116 (31%) patients. 169 (45%) patients completed a full course of treatment. In addition, 44% of patients who underwent liver biopsy prior to treatment completed treatment compared to 46% of patients who did not undergo liver biopsy prior to treatment. The standard ICD9 finding of an emotional well-being problem was not related to a higher discontinuation rate.

Conclusion: Taking everything into account, pretreatment liver biopsy was not a positive indicator for treatment culmination, and the presence of emotional well-being messes was not a negative indicator for treatment fruition.

Keywords: Liver Pretreatment Biopsy, Basic Diagnosis, Mental Health Disorders, Hepatitis C Treatment.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis C (HCV) is an exceptionally persistent hepatotoxic RNA infection that causes permanent necro inflammatory liver disease [1]. HCV seroprevalence is 2.2% worldwide, 1.6% in the United States, and as high as 15-16% in some Veterans Affairs Canada (VAC) clinical centers [2]. Normal comorbidity factors among the U.S. veteran population, such as advanced age, weight, HIV co-infection, immunosuppression, and alcohol intake, are related to the acceleration of liver disease and movement to cirrhosis in chronically HCV-infected patients. HCV-related cirrhosis (which affects 22% to 34% of HCV-infected individuals) causes increased horror and mortality due to end-stage liver failure and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), which may warrant liver transplantation. With this in mind, the goal of HCV treatment is to eliminate HCV RNA in an effort to prevent or delay the passage of the liver and, in addition, confusions [3]. The ideal target outcome of coordinated HCV treatment is a continuous virological response (SVR), which is characterized by an imperceptible HCV viral load (LV) 24 weeks after the end of treatment and signifies a fixation of the disease. A few factors are known to predict the likelihood of SVR with treatment with PEGylated interferon and ribavirin. In addition to HCV genotype, which has the most influence on SVR rates, the positive response to treatment is related to an HCV LV viral load of less than 600,000 IU/ml before treatment, female sex, at age not exactly 40 years, race/nationality other than Black/African-American, body weight less than 75 kg, non-appearance of insulin resistance, high ALT levels, and non-monitoring of fibrosis or related cirrhosis [4]. In VA, attributes related to a good response to treatment are under-represented because a large proportion of patients are male, more notable than 50 years of age, African-American, cirrhotic, with high HCV viral load and body weight greater than 75 kg. In addition, many patients infected with HCV in IL have other co-morbidities that limit the decency of HCV treatment, such as HIV coinfection, poorly controlled diabetes, low body weight, and mental problems including grief, post-traumatic stress disorder and schizophrenia, or ongoing substance abuse. Because these co-morbidities are not well addressed in most of the large preliminary randomized clinical trials for the treatment of HCV, it is difficult to extrapolate the findings from the literature distributed to the veteran population [5].

METHODOLOGY:

Due to the evolving nature of HCV treatment, we excluded patients whose HCV treatment was completed during the survey period but who had

started treatment prior to March 2019 to February 2020. Our current research was conducted at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from March 2019 to February 2020. We also excluded patients whose medications were administered under ideal conditions but who were recorded as having received less than one month of antiviral therapy or had never started treatment. This review agreement was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board of the Philadelphia Veterans Medical Center (VAMC). In the event that a patient had received multiple HCV treatments, data was collected on the last treatment as it is possible that a new treatment may be required if the patient is not following the treatment due to narrow-mindedness or lack of efficacy. Baseline data included age, race, sexual orientation, weight, HCV genotype, liver transplant status, liver fibrosis (by liver biopsy or fibrosies, when available) and critical comorbid conditions recorded on the HCV gauge prior to HCV treatment. The race was acquired through graphical documentation based on patient self-assessment. Results for emotional well-being and determination of diabetes were dictated by ICD9 codes, progress notes, and pharmacy medical records. HIV status was dictated by screening of research facilities when available. Standard information from research facilities was recorded as the last information archived one year before the first dose of interferon and ribavirin. Alcohol or substance abuse by assistants was recorded in the light of the progress notes. The start of the treatment routine and treatment changes were retrieved from the pharmacy files and from the progress notes. The dates of cessation of treatment were characterized as approximately one month after the date of filling the last remedy for interferon or ribavirin, unless explicitly expressed in the progress notes. The quantity of treatments was determined using pharmacy records, unless explicitly stated in the progress notes, as some patients may have recently been treated outside the VA system. Consumption rates were dictated by whether treatment was completed earlier than the predefined duration, as decided by the individual viral genotype and by supplier remarks in the progress notes. Explanations for early termination of treatment were recorded if explicitly expressed in the progress notes. Laboratory information, pharmacy records and progress notes were used to retrieve information on antagonistic effects. Fragility, neutropenia and thrombocytopenia occurring during treatment were recorded. Pharmacy records were used to decide whether developmental factors, such as erythropoietin or filgrastim, were used to treat particular antagonistic effects.

RESULTS:

A total of 468 patients were distinguished as receiving remedies for interferon PEGylate and ribavirin. 89 of the 467 subjects were avoided for the following reasons: 25 (28.4%) started treatment before January 2003; 39 (40.9%) took their first remedy without ever starting treatment; 17 (19.3%) discontinued treatment within 4 weeks due to adverse events; 13 (14.7%) took the primary remedy but had less than 4 long archived follow-up periods. Hence, a total of 379 HCV-treated patients were enrolled in the study. Of the 378 absolute subjects, 98% were male, 52% were dark racially based and 82% had genotype 1 or 4 contaminations (Table 1). The average age of the subjects included was 54 years (range 27-77 years). The mean BMI was 28.3 kg/m² (95% CI 19.8-58.6) where 39% of patients were overweight, 40% were corpulent and 4% were overweight beyond expectation. Mean pre-treatment

HCV titers were 1,350,000 IU/mL (range 346-26,500,000). The partner was diabetic, influencing 98 (27%) patients. HIV co-infection was available in 36 (8%), while 89 (23%) had no reported HIV assessment. A total of 252 (67%) patients received only one HCV treatment, as did 34% of patients who received two or more treatments. Substance abuse by caregivers was reported by 12 (4%) patients, while 32 (9%) patients reported alcohol use during treatment. Mental well-being problems were normal, with 228 (56.8%) patients (table 2) having a psychological well-being problem in any case. It was found that the subjects regularly suffered from a variety of mental well-being problems, with heavy problems, post-traumatic stress and tension problems, most of them turning to a doctor from time to time.

Table 1:

Mental health disorder, ICD-9 diagnosis	Frequency, <i>n</i>	%
Depressive disorder	125	42
Posttraumatic stress disorder	90	30
Anxiety disorder (not specified)/panic disorder/social phobia/obsessive compulsive disorder	37	12
Schizophrenia/psychosis/thought disorder	24	8
Bipolar disorder	13	4
Mood disorder (not specified)	7	2
Cognitive disorder/organic brain disorder	4	1
Personality disorder	4	1

Table 2:

TABLE 1. SUBJECTS CHARACTERISTICS BY DISEASE SEVERITY (14 – 170)

Characteristic	Mild disease Number (%)	Severe disease Number (%)	All patients Number (%)
Total number (%)	62 (42)	86 (58)	148 (100)
Age (mean, SD)	51 ± 8	52 ± 8	51 ± 8
Male	54 (87)	74 (86)	128 (87)
Hispanic	8 (13)	12 (14)	20 (14)
Race			
White (non-Hispanic)	32 (52)	35 (41)	67 (45)
Black	16 (26)	34 (40)	50 (34)
Married	16 (26)	20 (23)	36 (24)
At least some college education	34 (55)	33 (38)	67 (45)
Income > \$60,000	5 (8)	3 (4)	8 (5)
Employed	26 (42)	31 (36)	57 (39)
Veteran clinic	49 (79)	49 (57)	98 (66)
Number of medical comorbidities ^a			
Zero	18 (29)	23 (27)	41 (28)
One	26 (42)	33 (38)	59 (40)
Two or more	18 (29)	30 (35)	48 (32)
Excellent or very good overall health status ^b	16 (26)	13 (15)	29 (20)
HCV-related quality of life ^c (median, range)	17 (0–89)	21 (0–89)	19 (0–89)
Trust in physician ^d (median, range)	73 (45–100)	70 (45–100)	70 (45–100)
Patient choice predisposition ^e (median, range)	5 (0–10)	8 (0–10)	7 (0–10)
HCV genotype 1	52 (84)	73 (85)	125 (85)
HCV genotype 2	10 (16)	13 (15)	25 (16)
Alcohol abuse			
Never	18 (29)	34 (40)	52 (35)
Ever	44 (71)	52 (61)	96 (65)
Current	2 (3)	5 (6)	7 (5)
Substance abuse			
Never	6 (10)	14 (16)	20 (14)
Ever	56 (90)	72 (84)	128 (87)
Current	6 (10)	5 (6)	11 (7)
History of depression ^f	31 (50)	53 (62)	84 (57)

Notes: ^aBased on subjects' response to a predefined list of six comorbidities: hypertension, diabetes, lung disease, kidney disease, peptic ulcer disease, and mental illness; ^bbased on subjects' response to a validated questionnaire: (In general, I would say that my health is ... poor, fair, good, very good or excellent); ^cbased on a previously validated hepatitis C (HCV) quality of life scale encompassing eleven questions. Range of total score is 0–100 with higher scores representing worse quality of life; ^dbased on a previously validated trust in physician scale. Range of total score is 0–100 with higher scores representing greater trust in physician; ^echoice predisposition was ascertained based on a previously validated scale ranging from zero (I am certain that I do not want to be treated) to ten (I am certain that I do want to be treated). Higher scores reflect greater preference towards undergoing treatment; ^fdepression was measured using a previously validated two-question instrument that evaluates depressed mood and anhedonia.

Table 3:

Variables	Cohort (<i>n</i> = 375)
Gender	
Male, <i>n</i> (%)	367 (98%)
Female, <i>n</i> (%)	8 (2%)
Race/ethnicity	
Black, <i>n</i> (%)	192 (52%)
White, <i>n</i> (%)	141 (38%)
Unknown, <i>n</i> (%)	22 (6%)
Other, <i>n</i> (%)	20 (5%)
Genotype	
1 and 4, <i>n</i> (%)	301 (80%)
2 and 3, <i>n</i> (%)	58 (15%)
Not documented, <i>n</i> (%)	12 (3%)
Mixed, <i>n</i> (%)	4 (1%)
Age (years), median (range)	53 (27–77)
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.2 (18.7–59.5)
Obese (BMI 30 to 39.9), <i>n</i> (%)	149 (40%)
Overweight (BMI 25 to 29.9), <i>n</i> (%)	137 (37%)
Morbidly obese (BMI ≥ 40), <i>n</i> (%)	15 (4%)
HCV VL RNA (IU/mL), median (range)	1,350,000 (344–25,400,000)
Diabetes diagnosis, <i>n</i> (%)	97 (26%)
HIV diagnosis	
No, <i>n</i> (%)	253 (68%)
Not assessed or not documented, <i>n</i> (%)	87 (23%)
Yes, <i>n</i> (%)	35 (9%)
Course of therapy	
1st, <i>n</i> (%)	252 (67%)
2nd, <i>n</i> (%)	92 (25%)
3rd or more, <i>n</i> (%)	31 (8%)
Concomitant substance abuse, <i>n</i> (%)	11 (3%)
Concomitant alcohol use, <i>n</i> (%)	30 (8%)
Alb (g/dL), median (range)	4.2 (2.7–5.3)
Hgb (g/dL), median (range)	14.6 (9.8–18.2)
INR, median (range)	1.0 (0.86–1.78)
PLT (THO/uL), median (range)	197.5 (42–439)
SCr (mg/dL), median (range)	1.0 (0.6–3.5)
Tbili (mg/dL), median (range)	0.8 (0.1–2.9)
WBC (THO/uL), median (range)	6.2 (2.2–14.9)

DISCUSSION:

Our results show that there is no distinction in completion rates when considering the status of the biopsy in the year following the start of HCV treatment [6]. While biopsy status had no effect on the rate of treatment uptake, all things considered, the biopsy status associated with treatment uptake as the biopsy completion rate in this Table 3: Summary of uptake rate by amount of mental wellness problems [7]. Mix of psychological well-being at the schema level n (%), patients completed HCV treatment course** 0 62/151 (44%) 1 70/152 (48%) at least 2 37/73 (53%) **Chi-an investigation squared shows that no measurable distinction was found for consumption rates across these layers ($P = 0.34$). companion (24%) was overall more remarkable than the rate of liver biopsy in the untreated persistent hepatitis C population on which we focus (4.0%) [8]. We did not collect data at the provider level in this survey, but it is almost certain that provider practice style can have a significant impact on understanding attendance during treatment. In principle, patients with emotional well-being problems, according to the model, appear to be less likely to endure and complete a full course of HCV treatment, as they may be more sensitive to the antagonistic mental impact profile of interferon alpha [9]. To investigate the effect of a standard psychological well-being problem on HCV treatment completion rates, we evaluated whether the number of emotional well-being problems at the gauge influenced HCV treatment completion rates and the rates of treatment discontinuation identified with mental antagonistic impacts for patients with a comparative profile with those without psychological well-being problems. PEGylated interferon and ribavirin may cause indications of tension and misery at a frequency of 22-38%. Some tests have shown that almost half of the patients under antiviral treatment may present manifestations of tension, misery or cramps. Other studies have shown that interferon-induced gloom fundamentally contributes to the early discontinuation of treatment and hence to the reduction of SVR. Interestingly, our review showed that HCV treatment discontinuation rates due to adverse mental effects of the drugs were comparable between patients with a standard level of psychological well-being and those without a standard level of emotional well-being [10].

CONCLUSION:

All things considered, in this re-examination survey, liver biopsy performed within one year of starting HCV treatment was not related to the increased rates of treatment completion. Comparable rates of use were found among patients with no psychological well-

being problems at baseline, with a mixture of emotional well-being prior to treatment, and with at least two mental well-being problems at baseline. End of treatment due to adverse mental health effects of medication was comparable among patients who had little regard for their mental history.

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